

WOMEN SAFETY DEVICE USING IOT

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ABSTRACT

The project presents a wearable safety device for women using the Arduino. The purpose of this device is to safeguard women in the event they might face any danger. The device uses wireless sensor network to communicate and to send alerts to them. The GPS and GSM are used to share the used to share the user's location directly to the relevant authorities and saved contacts. The switch in the device work for sending manual alerts in case of emergency and as panic switch to get the shock, then the Buzzer will also activate along laser diode.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, women safety has become a major issue as they can't step out of their house at any given time due to physical/sexual abuse and a fear of violence. Even in the 21st century where the technology is rapidly growing and new gadgets were developed but still women's and girls are facing problems. Women are adept at mobilizing diverse groups for a common reason. They often work across ethnic, religious, political, and cultural divides to promote liberty. We are all aware of importance of women safety, but we must analyze that they should be properly protected. Women are not as physically fit as men ,in an emergency situation a helping

hand would be assistance for them. The best way to curtail your probability of becoming a dupe of violent crime (robbery, sexual assault, rape, domestic violence) is to recognize, defence and look up resources to help you out of hazardous situation.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Dr.C K Gomathy, Article: An Effective Innovation Technology In Enhancing Teaching And Learning Of Knowledge Using Ict Methods, International Journal Of Contemporary Research In Computer Science And Technology (Ijcrct) E-Issn: 2395-5325 Volume3, Issue 4,P.No-10-13, April '2017.

In the increasing of technology into teaching is one of the vital significance challenges for education today. All department academicians will agree that the contemporary world is going through the modern education trends. Every person is engaged in various kinds of computer related activities and using various multimedia content on internet either by various techniques. Moreover the modern education using ICT generated by various services such as offline/online teaching - forum in teacher to student interactions, assignments, debate, audio and video seminar and etc is also increasing the volume of ict to the larger extent. However the ICT challenges but it can also be utilized as the opportunities by the

computer techniques. Challenge in terms of difficulties in identifying the evidences from the technical problems behind in the features. This paper focuses on the use of technology in teaching-learning audio and video seminar process that will greatly contribute to the student needs for learning anywhere, anytime. It is time to move beyond the walls of classrooms to join forces with other institutions and societies to revitalize education trends. The Integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into teaching and learning process is a growing field which has variety of definitions according to different points of view.

Dr.C K Gomathy, Article: A Semantic Quality of Web Service Information Retrieval Techniques Using Bin Rank, International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science Engineering and Information Technology (IJSRCSEIT) Volume 3 | Issue 1 | ISSN : 2456-3307, P.No:1563-1578, February-2018.

This study seeks to understand the effects of technology on education: teaching and learning. All the data used in this study comes from secondary sources. Information was gathered from several sources, including peer-reviewed journal papers, published and unpublished dissertations, online and print textbooks, and encyclopaedias. Findings: Evidence on the effects of technology is contradictory, according to a review of the relevant literature. Thanks to information technology developments, classroom collaboration between teachers and students is more efficient than ever. It broadens their academic and intellectual horizons, making students more versatile in the classroom. Due to the internet's accessibility, remote learning

may now be supported by technological means. Students can use search engines to conduct research. Hardware failures, software incompatibilities between home and school, or non-existent internet connections, and outdated program versions are just some of the dependability problems that students and teachers face in the classroom. Because of developments in technology like graphical calculators, high-tech gadgets, and small cameras, dishonest students may now easily gain an edge over their classmates. Distractions in modern life may be traced back in large part to technological advancements. Students' health might be negatively impacted by excessive technology usage. The history of technology in education dates to the 1920s when radio broadcasting was first used to teach political science and history. In the 1950s, the computer-based teaching system, programmed logic for automatic teaching operations (PLATO), was developed at the University of Illinois. The 1960s saw the advent of audio and video cassettes which were used to deliver lectures and educational content.

Dr.C K Gomathy, Article: A Web Based Platform Comparison by an Exploratory Experiment Searching For Emergent Platform Properties, IAETSD Journal For Advanced Research In Applied Sciences, Volume 5, Issue 3, P.No-213-220, ISSN NO: 2394-8442,Mar/2018.

Rainfall prediction is important as heavy rainfall can lead to many disasters. The prediction helps people to take preventive measures and moreover the prediction should be accurate. There are two types of prediction short term rainfall prediction and long term rainfall. Prediction mostly short term prediction can gives us the accurate result. The main challenge is to build a model for

long term rainfall prediction. Heavy precipitation prediction could be a major drawback for earth science department because it is closely associated with the economy and lifetime of human. It's a cause for natural disasters like flood and drought that square measure encountered by individuals across the world each year. Accuracy of rainfall statement has nice importance for countries like India whose economy is basically dependent on agriculture. The dynamic nature of atmosphere, applied mathematics techniques fail to provide sensible accuracy for precipitation statement. The prediction of precipitation using machine learning techniques may use regression. Intention of this project is to offer non-experts easy access to the techniques, approaches utilized in the sector of precipitation prediction and provide a comparative study among the various machine learning techniques. Rainfall forecasting is very important because heavy and irregular rainfall can have many impacts like destruction of crops and farms, damage of property so a better forecasting model is essential for an early warning that can minimize risks to life and property and also managing the agricultural farms in better way. This prediction mainly helps farmers and also water resources can be utilized efficiently. Rainfall prediction is a challenging task and the results should be accurate. There are many hardware devices for predicting rainfall by using the weather conditions like temperature, humidity, pressure. These traditional methods cannot work in an efficient way so by using machine learning techniques we can produce accurate results. We can just do it by having the historical data analysis of rainfall and can predict the rainfall for future seasons.

Dr.C K Gomathy, Article: A Study on the Effect of Digital Literacy and information Management, IAETSD Journal For Advanced Research In Applied Sciences, Volume 7 Issue 3, P.No-51-57, ISSN NO: 2279-543X,Mar/2018.

Technological developments are currently playing a remarkable contribution in the life of modern society, and scientific knowledge becomes more impactful across numerous domains of society than any time ever. Digital literacy is underpinned by basic technical use of computers and the Internet. Digital literacy is the set of competencies required for full participation in a knowledge society. It includes knowledge, skills, and behaviors involving the effective use of digital devices such as Smartphone's, tablets, laptops and desktop PCs for purposes of communication, expression, collaboration and advocacy. The digital literacy initially focused on systematic digital skills and computers, the focus has moved from stand-alone to network devices including the World Wide Web and social media. Digital literacy is the marrying of the two terms digital and literacy. However, it is much more than a combination of the two terms. Digital information is a symbolic representation of data, and literacy refers to the ability to read for knowledge, write coherently, and think critically about the written word. Digital literacy is the set of competencies required for full participation in a knowledge society. It includes knowledge, skills, and behaviors involving the effective use of digital devices such as smart phones, tablets, laptops and desktop PCs for purposes of communication, expression, collaboration and advocacy. While digital literacy initially focused on digital skills and stand-alone computers, the focus has shifted from stand-alone to network devices including the Internet and social media. Digital literacy is distinct from computer literacy and digital skills. Computer literacy preceded digital literacy. Computer literacy refers to knowledge and skills in using traditional computers, such as desktop PCs and laptops.

Dr.C K Gomathy, Article: A Semantic Quality of Web Service Information Retrieval Techniques Using Bin Rank A Cloud Monitoring Framework Perform in Web Services, International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science Engineering and Information Technology IJSRCSEIT | Volume 3 | Issue 5 | ISSN : 2456-3307,May-2018.

Disease Prediction using Machine Learning is the system that is used to predict the diseases from the symptoms which are given by the patients or any user. The system processes the symptoms provided by the user as input and gives the output as the probability of the disease. Naïve Bayes classifier is used in the prediction of the disease which is a supervised machine learning algorithm. The probability of the disease is calculated by the Naïve Bayes algorithm. With an increase in biomedical and healthcare data, accurate analysis of medical data benefits early disease detection and patient care. By using linear regression and decision tree we are predicting diseases like Diabetes, Malaria, Jaundice, Dengue, and Tuberculosis. Machine Learning is the domain that uses past data for predicting. Machine Learning is the understanding of computer system under which the Machine Learning model learn from data and experience. The machinelearning algorithm has two phases: 1) Training & 2) Testing. To predict the disease from a patient's symptoms and from the history of the patient, machine learning technology is struggling from past decades. Healthcare issues can be solved efficiently by using Machine Learning Technology. We are applying complete machine learning concepts to keep the track of patient's health. ML model allows us to build models to get quickly cleaned and processed data and deliver results faster. By using this system doctors will make good decisions related to patient diagnoses and according to that, good treatment will be given to the patient, which increases improvement in patient healthcare services. To introduce machine learning in the medical field, healthcare is the prime example. To

improve the accuracy of large data, the existing work will be done on unstructured or textual data. For the prediction of diseases, the existing will be done on linear, KNN, Decision Tree algorithm.

EXISTING SYSTEM

In previous system the alert system for the women is done through the application. For the security purpose the applications contain the SOS number which will alert the family members of the victim.

Disadvantages of existing system:

- Victim's phone may lose
- Battery may die

PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system we here designed equipment for alerting the system. In this project we here used the Arduino controller for the controlling the whole process of the system. The GSM is used to send SMS regarding GPS locations. LCD is for displaying and switch is pressed when the person is in danger. Here we are adding Buzzer Laser Diode which will activate when the women press the switch.

Block diagram

ARUDINO:

The Arduino is a family of microcontroller boards to simplify electronic design, prototyping and experimenting for artists, hackers, hobbyists, but also many professionals. People use it as brains for their robots, to build new digital music instruments, or to build a system that lets your house plants tweet you when they're dry. Arduinos (we use the standard Arduino Uno) are built around an ATmega microcontroller — essentially a complete computer with CPU, RAM, Flash memory, and input/output pins, all on a single chip. Unlike, say, a Raspberry Pi, it's designed to attach all kinds of sensors, LEDs, small motors and speakers, servos, etc. directly to these pins, which can read in or output digital or analog voltages between 0 and 5 volts. The Arduino connects to your computer via USB, where you program it in a simple language (C/C++, similar to Java) from inside the free Arduino IDE by uploading your compiled code to the board. Once programmed, the Arduino can run with the USB link back to your computer, or stand-alone without it — no keyboard or screen needed, just power.

Heart beat

The front of the sensor, with the heart logo, is where you put your finger. You'll also notice a tiny circular opening through which the Kingbright's reverse mounted green LED shines.

Just beneath the circular opening is a small ambient light photo sensor – [APDS-9008](#) from Avago. This sensor is similar to the ones used in cell phones, tablets, and laptops to adjust the screen's brightness based on the ambient lighting conditions.

On the back of the module are an MCP6001 Op-Amp from Microchip and a few resistors and capacitors that make up the R/C filter network. Additionally, there is a reverse protection diode to prevent damage in the event that the power leads are accidentally reversed.

The theory behind optical heart-rate sensors is very simple. If you've ever shined a flashlight through your fingers and observed your heartbeat pulsing, the concept of optical heart-rate pulse sensors can be easily grasped.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic (a piezo transducer). BeStar produces

Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications)

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications) is a cellular network, which means that mobile phones connect to it by searching for cells in the immediate vicinity. GSM networks operate in four different frequency ranges. Most GSM networks operate in the 900 MHz or 1800 MHz bands. Some countries in the Americas use the 850 MHz and 1900 MHz bands because the 900 and 1800 MHz frequency bands were already allocated. The rarer 400 and 450 MHz frequency bands are assigned in some countries, where these frequencies were previously used for first-generation systems. GSM-900 uses 890–915 MHz

to send information from the mobile station to the base station (uplink) and 935–960 MHz for the other direction (downlink), providing 124 RF channels (channel numbers 1 to 124) spaced at 200 kHz. Duplex spacing of 45 MHz is used. In some countries the GSM-900 band has been extended to cover a larger frequency range. This 'extended GSM', E-GSM, uses 880–915 MHz (uplink) and 925–960 MHz (downlink), adding 50 channels (channel numbers 975 to 1023 and 0) to the original GSM-900 band. Time division multiplexing is used to allow eight full-rate or sixteen half-rate speech channels per radio frequency channel. There are eight radio timeslots (giving eight burst periods) grouped into what is called a TDMA frame. Half rate channels use alternate frames in the same timeslot. The channel data rate is 270.833 kbit/s, and the frame duration is 4.615 ms.

RELAY MODULE

Relay modules are simply circuit boards that house one or more relays. They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but are most commonly rectangular with 2, 4, or 8 relays mounted on them, sometimes even up to a 16 relays. Relay modules contain other components than the relay unit. These include indicator LEDs, protection diodes, transistors, resistors, and other parts. But what is the module relay, which makes the

bulk of the device? You may ask. Here are facts to note about it:

- A relay is an electrical switch that can be used to control devices and systems that use higher voltages. In the case of module relay, the mechanism is typically an [electromagnet](#).
- The relay module input voltage is usually DC. However, the electrical load that a relay will control can be either AC or DC, but essentially within the limit levels that the relay is designed for.
- A relay module is available in an array of input voltage ratings: It can be a 3.2V or 5V relay module for low power switching, or it can be a 12 or 24V relay module for heavy-duty systems.
- The relay module information is normally printed on the surface of the device for ready reference. This includes the input voltage rating, switch voltage, and current limit.

CONCLUSION

The proposed design will deal with critical issues faced by women during the night and provide security with advanced technology.

While society may or may not change its mindset but this device is will help to feel women independent.

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